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Kinyongia multituberculata (NIEDEN, 1913) introduced in Kenya (Reptilia: Chamaeleonidae)

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INTRODUCTION

Kinyongia multituberculata (NIEDEN, 1913), The West-Usambara Two-Horned Chameleon, sometimes also referred as West-Usambara Blade-Horned chameleon, is an endemic to the high altitudes of West Usambara Mountains in NE-Tanzania. Occupying the forest-edge, it penetrates the agricultural land of the high altitudes and builds there very strong populations (NEČAS, PERS.OBS.; TILBURY 2010; TOLLEY & AL. 2014).

Having been described as *Chamaeleon fischeri multituberculatus* by NIEDEN (1913), who put him to the complex of Two-Horned or Blade-Horned Chameleons of E Africa as a subspecies of *Kinyongia fischeri* (REICHENOW, 1887), and as such, it was handled till 2008, when MARIAUX ET AL. (2008) reviewed the whole complex and elevated the subspecies into alone-standing species. The list of the two-bladed African chameleons, restricted with their occurrence to the Arch Mountains of Kenya and Tanzania is nowadays as follows (TILBURY, 2010; GLAW, 2015):

Kinyongia boehmei (LUTZMANN & NEČAS 2002)

Kinyongia fischeri (REICHENOW, 1887)

Kinyongia matschiei (WERNER, 1895)

Kinyongia multituberculata (NIEDEN, 1913)

Kinyongia tavetana (STEINDACHNER, 1891)

Kinyongia uluguruensis (LOVERIDGE, 1957)

Kinyongia vosseleri (NIEDEN, 1913)

Out of them, only two species occur on the Kenyan territory:

Kinyongia boehmei (Taita Hills) and *Kinyongia tavetana* (Chyulu and northern foothills of Mt. Kilimanjaro; based on the study of two voucher specimens in the National Museum of Kenya, the Chyulu Population is very probably an alone standing, yet undescribed species – P. NEČAS PERS. OBS.).

Fig 1. *Kinyongia multituberculata* from Lushoto (W. Usambara Mts., Tanzania) male; Photo PETR NEČAS

Kinyongia multituberculata differs from all two-horned chameleon species in East Africa by its dorsal crest, formed by significantly enlarged conical scales extending in males along the whole length of back and continue to half of tail without any interruption where it becomes inconspicuous... Therefore, it is easy to identify.

While a vast majority of chameleon populations in Africa are indigenous, some were introduced by humans to previously uninhabited territories. The pet trade or private naturalists contribute to these introductions significantly. Individual feral specimens are occasionally found in various places; however, they seldom build breeding populations and they disappear mostly as quickly as they appear.

In Kenya, there are no known feral chameleon populations, with the exception of a notoriously famous introduction of the Oustalet's Chameleon *Furcifer oustaleti* (MOCQUARD, 1894) from Madagascar in the seventies of 20th century. Only two specimens were collected, and no

further appearance has been reported since 1974, when the collected specimens were deposited to the collections of the National Museum of Kenya. (TILBURY, 2010)

OBSERVATIONS

Not later than since 2014, the second author reports here on the uninterrupted series of rare but regular sightings of *K. multituberculata* in Karen, Nairobi and provides photographic evidence. It is unknown who was the source of the introduction and what was the purpose of it.

Fig 2. *Kinyongia multituberculata* from Karen (Nairobi, Kenya) male; Photo BELINDA LEVITAN

- 2014: First sighting in a creeper on the side of a neighbour's house.
- 2016 April: Crossing Windy ridge.
- 2016 July: Crossing Windy ridge.
- 2017 June: In a garden. This one came charging down an Albizia tree - possibly chasing a male of *Trioceros jacksonii* which dropped out of the tree before *K. multituberculata* caught attention. It came down to the fork and then turned around and went up again.
- 2018 July: This was found when cutting a huge clump of bamboo about 70 metres from our house, brought by staff. It was released onto a creeper against the house, but it moved on. It was found on the ground the next day, so it was taken to a bed with more vegetation.
- 2018 September: A young male found crossing Windy Ridge. Sadly, found a while later, fallen foul of the lawn mower.
- 2018 October: One adult male stayed on the same shrub in the garden for about a week (posing) and then disappeared.
- 2019 January: Found by gardener while clipping the hedge.
- 2020 July: Found in the garden.

It is interesting that all the observations were made on different males, in one case it is possible that it was a repeated sighting. Presence of different individuals of different size categories indicates that reproduction takes place. Not finding females is nothing exceptional, as they are much smaller, more cryptically coloured and also less exposing themselves to areas outside of bushes, while males are usually quite active and expose themselves to the space to impose other males. The species has been demonstrated to be able to live more than 10 years in captivity (NEČAS & MANČEN 2020), the life expectancy in the wild is much lower due mainly to predation, parasites and diseases.

The observations mentioned here are confirmed by observations and photo evidence of SILKE ROTH (2020, PERS. OBS.), who meets them during last years on a daily basis in her plot. Individual animals are recognized and both males as well as females (some gravid) are found as well as hatchlings and juveniles.

One picture was taken from Flickr and published at chameleondatabase.com

DISCUSSION

Karen is a south-west suburb of Nairobi, bordering the Ngong Forest. It is a residential area known for its large European population, somewhat isolated and inhabited by mid to high-income residents. The vicinity of Ngong forest and the relatively large plots with houses and villas is quite shady and green. Thanks to the extensive gardens full of trees, it is a natural habitat of three other indigenous Kenyan chameleon species:

High-Casqued Von-Höhnel's Chameleon – *Trioceros hoehnelii* (STEINDACHNER, 1891) (in nominotypic subspecies)

Jackson's Three-Horned Chameleon – *Trioceros jacksonii* (BOULENGER, 1896) (in nominotypic subspecies)

Flap-Necked Chameleon *Chamaeleo dilepis* LEACH, 1819 (in the high-altitude form "roperi").

Fig 3. *Kinyongia multituberculata* from Karen (Nairobi, Kenya) female and juvenile; Photo SILKE ROTH

Their interaction with the feral species has not been recorded. It is questionable whether *K. multituberculata* represents any serious threat for the local herpetofauna, as the niche already co-occupied by three other chameleon species of similar size, which are rather common in the area (sensu lato). The scarcity of sightings of this species gives us no info about the potential threat, they might represent. Remarkable is, however, the fact, that on the plots, occupied by *K. multituberculata*, only twice for the whole observed period, another chameleon species was observed:

one single baby of *Trioceros hoehnelii*,
one male of *Trioceros jacksonii*.

Fig 4. *Kinyongia multituberculata* from Karen (Nairobi, Kenya) male; Photo BELINDA LEVITAN

As in the West Usambara Mts., the vast montane area is occupied by this species only, it might indicate a certain aggressivity towards other chameleon species, that might have been eradicated, especially when evidently, the biotope inhabited by this species has been extended by agriculture and other species. Only *Rhampholeon spinosus* nowadays, are confined to the remnants of primary and secondary forests there. The chameleon fauna composition of the West Usambaras is very poor if compared to both next-laying Mountains, which are homes to more chameleon species. The East Usambara Mountains are inhabited namely by 8 Chameleon species, 2 of which are endemic to the mountains:

Chamaeleo dilepis LEACH, 1819 (in nominotypic subspecies),
Kinyongia matschiei (WERNER, 1895) (endemic),
Kinyongia tenuis (MATSCHIE, 1892),
Kinyongia vosseleri (NIEDEN, 1913) (endemic),
Rhampholeon spinosus (MATSCHIE, 1892),
Rhampholeon temporalis (MATSCHIE, 1892),

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Rieppeleon brevicaudatus (MATSCHIE, 1892),
Trioceros deremensis (MATSCHIE, 1892).

and the PS Pare Mountains by three chameleon species, all of which are endemic (see notes):

Kinyongia cf. *tavetana* (STEINDACHNER, 1891) (based on scalation and isolated range, it is very probably an endemic, separate, yet undescribed species – P. NEČAS PERS. OBS.),

Kinyongia uthmoelleri (MÜLLER, 1938) (based on morphology and isolated range, *Kinyongia arytator* LUTZMANN & AL., 2010 is very probably an endemic, separate species – P. NEČAS PERS. OBS.),
Rhampholeon spinosus (MATSCHIE, 1892).

Long term observations should monitor the situation before possible eradication measures might be organized, as in general, feral populations of reptiles are considered as unwanted and can represent a danger for local fauna due to competition and/or predation.

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Fig 5. *Kinyongia multituberculata* from Karen (Nairobi, Kenya) male and juvenile; Photo SILKE ROTH

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Fig 6. *Kinyongia multituberculata* from Lushoto (W. Usambara Mts., Tanzania) male; Photo PETR NEČAS